

SymPyCAP

PSSOH post-conference

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Initial motivation

- Electric Circuit Theory Course (<http://tek.etf.rs>)
- SALECx ([Tosić D. & Potrebić M. 2019](#))
- Python

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Mentors

- Professor PhD Milka Potrebić
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Future work

- GUI / Schematic capture
- Solved circuits database

Thank you!
Enjoy!

Source code:

github.com/mdodovic/SymPyCAP